

Quantitative Spatial Analysis of Soil Properties at Four Soil Units in the Nigerian Southern Guinea Savanna Zone

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Abstract: Soil is a dynamic natural resource. Research has shown that variation in soil properties occur in any square meter, equivalent to the size of a pedon, in a natural landscape. Data, based on soil samples were taken with soil auger (Depth: 0 – 40) at four study sites (Gab, Ses, Zak and Anf). The data that were generated were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to determine the significant variations in the mean values of the measured soil parameters. Results indicated significant ($P < 0.05$) contrast in the soil properties considered between the four locations studied. Soils from Ses contained significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher silt (19.5%) and total N (0.70gkg^{-3}). Soils from Gab were higher in pH (5.6) while soils from Zak had higher sand content (76.6%). Soils from Anf had significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher organic carbon (4.9g kg^{-3}), available P (13.0gcm^{-3}), clay (27.3%), bulk density (1.54gcm^{-3}), total exchangeable bases ($0.49 \text{cmol}(+) \text{kg}^{-1}$), base saturation (63.8%), cation exchange capacity ($5.1 \text{cmol}(+) \text{kg}^{-1}$) and exchangeable bases than in soils of other locations. The significant difference recorded is an indication that the concentration and/or availability of soil properties varies with sampling distance.

Keywords: *Soil pH, Organic carbon, Cation Exchange Capacity, Spatial variation*

Introduction

Until the 1880s when soil was recognized as a natural body - worthy of study, it was simply considered as a 'uniform' loose fraction of the earth crust. The challenge of soil variability

has since continued to receive the needed attention and has warranted a review (Beckett, 1971 and Webster, 1985). Although soils may be derived from the same parent material under the same geographical location,

climatic conditions and ‘seemingly’ same topographic level, they may vary greatly in their characteristics (Brady and Weil, 2002). This variation may be largely due to the dynamic physical, chemical and biological activities in a given soil unit. Corwin (2012) itemized soil related spatial variable factors that influence crop yields as anthropogenic, topography, biological and meteorological. Igbal et al. (2005) added that spatial variability of soil properties in any field position is inherent in nature due to geologic and pedologic soil forming factors though some of the variability may be induced by tillage and other management practices.

It has been shown that soil variability generally increases with increase in the size of the area sampled (Webster, 1985). Brady and Weil (2002) reported that in a natural landscape, up to 40 percent of the total variance in soil properties occur within a distance of any m^2 , which is equivalent to the

size of a pedon. In spite of the realization of these variations however, soil samples continued to be taken from one or few profiles with the assumption that the properties measured at a point is a representative of the unsampled neighborhood.

A sound understanding of the variability of soil properties is necessary for making reliable interpretation and for minimizing sampling errors (Raji and Halidu, 1998). It is also a prerequisite for soil and crop-specific management (Sharma et al., 2011). The products of spatial analysis of soil properties will be very helpful to agricultural land users and land use policy makers in producing new management plans that are economically viable. The main aim of the study is therefore to assess and document significant variability in soil properties between four soil units and also to determine the degree of inter relationship between soil properties in each soil unit.

Figure 1 Map showing the study area

Figure 2 Map showing the sampling points

Materials and Methods

Site Description

Four study sites, 5 - 6 Km apart were selected within the Southern guinea savanna of north central Nigeria. The study area lies between latitudes 09° 07' and 12° 07' north and longitudes 06°02' and 09° 02' east (Figure 1). The average annual rainfall is about 1,300mm which falls between the months of April and October. The mean daily maximum temperature is about 32°C. The geology is mainly of sedimentary rocks (Barbour *et al.*, 1982). The soils in the area were classified as dominantly Typic Haplustult (Kolo, 2008).

Field Studies

Following identified topographic positions, soil samples were collected from four locations which are Anfani (Anf), Sheshi Ewowara (Ses), Gaba (Gab) and Zakan (Zak) as shown in Figure 2. The average distance between the sample points is 5057.77 m (Table 1). The soil samples were collected from the depth of 0 – 40 cm at each location using soil auger. The samples were packaged in properly labeled polythene bags and transported to soil science laboratory for the physico-chemical analyses.

Table 1 Spatial distance between sample points

	Origin	Destination	Distance (m)
1.	Anf	Gab	4729.09
2.	Anf	Ses	4868.07
3.	Anf	Zak	7189.62
4.	Gab	Ses	5196.84
5.	Gab	Zak	3075.93
6.	Ses	Zak	5287.04
Average			5057.77

Laboratory Analyses

The soils were air-dried and sieved through a sieve of a 2-mm gauge. Particle size distribution was determined by the hydrometer method. Bulk density was determined by Kerosene saturation method (Black *et al.*, 1982). Soil pH determination

was at a ratio 1:1 in distilled water and 1:2 CaCl₂. Organic carbon was determined using the dichromate oxidation method of Walkley-Black (Nelson and Sommers, 1982). The total nitrogen content was determined using the macrokjeldahl method (Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982). Available P was extracted

using the Bray – 1 method (Bray and Kurtz, 1945) and determined using the electro spectrophotometer. Exchangeable cationic bases (Ca, Mg, Na, K) were extracted by the ammonium acetate saturation method (Thomas, 1982). Calcium and Mg were determined on the atomic absorption Spectrophotometer while Na and K by flame photometer. Cation exchange capacity was determined from the leachate using the ammonium acetate saturation method at pH7 (Page *et al.*, 1982). Total exchangeable acidity was determined with NaOH. Effective cation exchangeable capacity (ECEC) was by the summation of exchangeable bases and exchangeable acidity. Percent base saturation was determined by the summation of exchangeable bases divided by cation exchange capacity multiplied by 100.

Statistical Analyses

The data generated from laboratory analysis were statistically analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Means that were statistically significant were separated using the least significant difference (LSD).

Results and Discussion

Mean data on some physical properties of the four sites studied are shown in Table 2. Soils from Zak had significantly ($P<0.05$) higher

sand fraction (76.6%) while Ses had higher silt (19.5%). Soils from Anf with a textural characteristic of sandy clay loam had significantly ($P<0.05$) higher clay content (27.3%) and bulk density value (1.54gcm^{-3}).

Variations in soil properties recorded between the four soil units (Figures 3 to 7) studied conforms to the findings of Raji and Halidu (1998) that soil variability generally increases with the size and/or the number of the areas sampled. Significant ($P<0.05$) variations in particle size distribution may be attributed to variations in weathering intensities and vegetation density resulting in differential rates of soil erosion, consequent upon selective transport of soil materials. Bulk density variations between soil units may be due to differential particle size distribution, soil compaction, tillage practices and/or organic matter contents. Brady and Weil (2002) and Ahn (1993) earlier reported some interacting factors which influence bulk density values as particle size distribution, soil compaction and organic matter content.

Mean pH values (in H_2O) and in (CaCl_2) were significantly higher in soils from Gab than in soils from other units (Table 3). However, significantly ($P<0.05$) lower pH in soils from Anf corresponds with the higher total exchangeable acidity (Table 3) in the same

soil unit. Nsokpo and Ibanga (2001) earlier reported that decrease in pH results in increase in exchangeable acidity and vice versa. Variations in pH and total

exchangeable acidity might have resulted from variations in the rate of leaching of cationic bases.

Table 2 Mean values of soil physical properties at different soil units in the Nigerian southern guinea savanna zone

Soil Units	pH			Texture	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)
	Sand (g kg ⁻¹)	Silt (g kg ⁻¹)	clay (g kg ⁻¹)		
Gab	670.4b	180.0a	140.6b	sl	1.27d
Ses	690.1b	190.5a	110.4c	sl	1.35b
Zak	760.6a	140.0ab	90.4c	sl	1.34c
Anf	540.8c	170.9a	270.3a	scl	1.54a
LSD(P<0.05)	4.65	4.48	2.43		0.01

Table 3 Mean values of pH, organic carbon (g kg⁻¹), total nitrogen (g kg⁻¹) and available P (mg kg⁻¹) at different soil units in the Nigerian southern guinea savanna zone

Soil Units	pH		Org. C	Total N	Avl. P
	H ₂ O	CaCl ₂			
Gab	5.6a	4.7a	2.4c	0.36c	7.9c
Ses	5.3c	4.4b	3.8b	0.70a	8.6b
Zak	5.5b	4.6a	1.3d	0.20d	5.8d
Anf	5.0d	4.0c	4.9a	0.55b	13.0a
LSD(P<0.05)	0.07	0.11	0.23	0.02	0.28

Org. C = Organic Carbon, Total N = Total Nitrogen, Avl P = Available Phosphorus

Figure 3 Maps showing the variations in particle size fractions and bulk density

Figure 4 Maps showing the variations in Soil pH, Organic Carbon and Total Nitrogen

Figure 5 Maps showing the variations in available phosphorus, exchangeable calcium, magnesium and Sodium

Figure 6 Maps showing the variations in potassium, total exchangeable acidity, CEC and ECEC

Figure 7 Map showing the variations in Base saturation

Mean values of organic carbon (4.9gkg^{-1}), available P (13.0mgkg^{-1}), CEC ($5.1\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) and ECEC ($3.9\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) were significantly ($P<0.05$) higher in soils from Anf (Tables 3 and 3). Total N (0.70gkg^{-1}) was higher in soils from Ses. Significant ($P<0.05$) higher organic carbon, available P and CEC (Tables 2 and 3) in soils from Anf corresponds with higher clay content (Table 2). This is an indication that appreciable amounts of clay are able to protect chemical

properties of soils from losses. Variations in the rate of litter input and decomposition may also, likely be responsible for variations in organic matter contents, total N and available P. Significantly ($P<0.05$) higher ECEC ($3.9\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) corresponds with higher exchangeable bases and higher total exchangeable acidity in soils from Anf (Table 4).

Mean values of exchangeable bases (Table 4) indicates that soils from Anf had significantly ($P<0.05$) higher Ca, Mg, Na and K contents (2.38, 0.46, 0.11 and 0.26 $\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$ respectively). Higher contents of exchangeable bases in Anf soil unit align with higher organic carbon content (Table 3) and CEC (Table 4) in the same soil location. Drake and Motto (1982) related high levels of exchangeable bases to high contributions of organic carbon and clay fractions of the CEC of the soil. Significant ($P<0.05$) variations in the contents of exchangeable bases between

soil units may therefore be attributed to variations in organic carbon contents and CEC of soil (Figure 6).

Base saturation in soils from Anf (63.8%) was significantly ($P<0.05$) higher, same as exchangeable bases (Figure 7). This is a pointer that base saturation and exchangeable bases are related, thus the availability or otherwise, of one may influence the other. Wild (1988) earlier reported that high contents of exchangeable bases could lead to high levels of base saturation.

Table 4 Mean values of exchangeable soil properties ($\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) at different soil units in the Nigerian southern guinea savanna zone.

Soil Units	Exch. Bases				TEA	CEC	ECEC	BS(%)
	Ca	Mg	Na	K				
$\text{cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$								
Gab	1.38b	0.35c	0.08b	0.19b	0.31c	4.8a	2.3b	43.4b
Ses	1.22c	0.40b	0.04c	0.12c	0.38b	4.4bc	2.2c	40.8c
Zak	1.22c	0.35c	0.04c	0.10d	0.30c	4.5ab	2.1d	39.1d
Anf	2.38a	0.46a	0.11a	0.26a	0.49a	5.1a	3.9a	63.8a
LSD($P<0.05$)	0.08	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.32	0.08	0.66

Ca = Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, Na = Sodium, K = Potassium, TEA = Total Exchangeable Acid, CEC = Cation Exchange Capacity, ECEC = Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, BS = Base Saturation

Conclusion

Soil properties were generally rated low at the four soil units studied (Table 4). However, results indicate that the Anf soil unit is generally more fertile with significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher organic carbon, total N, available P, CEC and exchangeable bases and therefore capable of supplying more nutrients than the soils from other three soil units. Variations in soil properties between the studied locations have shown that soils formed from the same parent material under the same geographical and climatic conditions could vary in their characteristics. The study also revealed that a nexus exist between soil properties. Thus, soil properties are inter dependent on each other in any given soil unit and the contents of one may largely depend on the availability of others. Considering the low status of organic carbon and total N, co-application of organic and inorganic fertilizers to all the soil units will be beneficial to the crops grown.

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